

**A QUALITATIVE STUDY IN THE PHILIPPINE EDUCATIONAL LANDSCAPE ON THE
PERSPECTIVES ON THE TEACHER LEADERSHIP CHALLENGES:
A CORRESPONDENCE ARTICLE**

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ABSTRACT

This correspondence article examines the difficulties and possibilities encountered by teacher leaders in the Philippines, as outlined in Alegado's research. It emphasizes problems such as leadership focused on principals and inadequate teacher training, leading to minimal teacher participation in school development initiatives. Teachers also experience limitations under conventional leadership frameworks. To tackle these difficulties, the study proposes promoting teacher leadership, utilizing the current K-12 curriculum reform, and providing focused leadership training. Despite persistent obstacles, these tactics are designed to improve collaboration and efficacy in education. The research reveals intricacies and perceives the recent curriculum revision as an opportunity to redefine teacher leadership in the Philippines. Policymakers and educators can utilize these observations to effectively navigate and enhance teacher leadership within the ever-changing educational environment of the country.

Keywords: *Teacher Leadership, Philippines Education, Challenges in Education, K-12 Curriculum Reform, Educational Strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Within the dynamic realm of education, teachers assume functions that extend beyond conventional classroom bounds, encompassing leadership duties that significantly shape the learning environment. This transition is especially noticeable in the Philippines, a country with a varied and vibrant educational environment. As educators assume leadership positions, they confront various complex difficulties that significantly influence the direction of teaching and learning. Alegado (2018) highlights that the specific constraints faced in the Philippine setting substantially affect the implementation of educational leadership. The study by Emerissa Jane Tendero (2023) examines the difficulties of public school leadership in the Zamboanga Peninsula

Region. It specifically focuses on how leadership effectiveness is affected by resource limitations, administrative challenges, and socio-cultural issues. Although facing these difficulties, the study proposes possible ways for expansion and improvement, highlighting the significance of community involvement, professional advancement, and inventive governance methods. In addition, Oracion's (2010) exhaustive examination further explores the complexities of leadership in public schools in the Philippines, offering valuable perspectives on practical elements and unique difficulties in this context.

These studies emphasize the fundamental change in the role of educators - from just facilitating learning to becoming leaders in the educational environment. They highlight the crucial significance of providing assistance and comprehending these developing responsibilities in the continuous education revolution in the Philippines and worldwide.

This study used a qualitative approach to investigate the viewpoints and firsthand encounters of educators in the Philippines, with a specific emphasis on the nation's educational environment. The research aims to elucidate the many facets of educational leadership, providing insights that enhance comprehension of the intricacies of the Philippine educational system. This study, presented as a letter article, seeks to facilitate dialogue by providing unique perspectives obtained from educators deeply involved in the complex educational landscape of the Philippines. In this investigation, the researcher aims to contribute to the continuing discussion on issues in educational leadership. The goal is to facilitate a collaborative effort to confront and overcome the obstacles individuals face in the vanguard of education.

Research Questions

In the dynamic landscape of Philippine education, teacher leaders play a crucial role in shaping how students learn. To comprehend the challenges they encounter and gain insight into teachers' perceptions of their roles, the exploration is guided by two fundamental research questions.

Research question 1: What are the specific challenges experienced by teacher leaders in the Philippines, and how do these challenges influence the teaching and learning process?

Research question 2: How do teachers perceive their leadership roles in the Philippines, and what strategies can be employed to address the associated challenges and support teacher leadership?

METHODOLOGY

This article examines teacher leaders' practical and perceptual issues in the Philippines. The topic was selected due to its capacity for a detailed examination of the problems faced by teacher leaders in the Philippines. Data was acquired through an extensive literature study rather than by conducting interviews to gain primary data. The researcher did a comprehensive literature review on the topic, meticulously citing the authors and publishers of the papers, reports, and other relevant sources. The process entails acquainting oneself with the data, searching for patterns, evaluating these patterns, establishing and labeling them, and ultimately generating a report.

DISCUSSION

This correspondence aims to examine the difficulties encountered by teacher leaders in the Philippines and to understand the many factors that influence their experiences and responsibilities.

Research question 1: What are the specific challenges experienced by teacher leaders in the Philippines, and how do these challenges influence the teaching and learning process?

According to Alegado's (2018) study, teacher leaders in the Philippines encounter distinct problems that impact the teaching and learning process.

1. Principal-centric leadership: The educational system in the Philippines has always focused on the principal's role. Consequently, the school principal possesses the majority of decision-making authority, limiting the opportunities for teachers to exert leadership inside the school.
2. Insufficient leadership training and teacher categorization: Teachers frequently need more training in leadership to assume leadership positions. Moreover, the teacher classification system in the Philippines needs to promote teachers' assumption of leadership positions.

These issues restrict the involvement of teachers in the school and impact the teaching and learning process by promoting a hierarchical decision-making approach and reducing the chances for teachers to contribute to initiatives aimed at improving the school. This can affect the caliber of education and the academic achievements of students.

Research question 2: How do teachers perceive their leadership roles in the Philippines, and what strategies can be employed to address the associated challenges and support teacher leadership?

According to Alegado's research, teachers in the Philippines believe that their leadership responsibilities are restricted because of the traditional emphasis on principals' authority and the absence of leadership education. This impression is additionally influenced by the teacher categorization system, which fails to encourage teachers to assume leadership positions.

To tackle these difficulties and promote teacher leadership, Alegado proposes the following strategies:

1. Foster Teacher Leadership: Advocate for implementing teacher leadership within the local setting. This can significantly impact the culture of their institutions, enhance student learning, and influence the practices of their colleagues.
2. Capitalize on Educational Reform: Take advantage of the recent implementation of the K-12 curriculum as a means to foster teacher leadership.
3. Offer leadership training: Provide instructors with essential leadership abilities through training and programs focused on professional development.

Through the use of these measures, it is feasible to surmount the obstacles linked to teacher leadership and establish a more cooperative and efficient educational milieu.

CONCLUSIONS

The study employs a qualitative approach by conducting focus group discussions and individual interviews with teachers from various jurisdictions in the Philippines. Additionally, it involves a meticulous evaluation of the educational reform implemented in the nation.

The research demonstrates that the concept of teacher leadership encounters difficulties in flourishing inside school organizations as a result of two primary phenomena. The nature of leadership in the system is traditionally focused on the principal and deeply ingrained. The second issue pertains to the need for more leadership training and adherence to the teacher categorization system. These limitations severely restrict how teachers can contribute to the school's functioning.

This paper proposes that implementing teacher leadership within the local educational context, following the adoption of the K-12 curriculum as part of recent educational reform, can significantly impact the school culture, enhance student learning, and influence the teaching practices of other educators.

The research additionally highlights issues in the execution of the K-12 curriculum in the country, such as a shortage of teachers, an unsustainable curriculum, inadequate resources and infrastructure, and a lack of coordination among various governmental entities.

Ultimately, this study offers significant perspectives on the obstacles and possibilities surrounding teacher leadership in the Philippines. It can serve as a beneficial tool for policymakers and educational professionals.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms that the author reviewed this study.

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